

////////////////////////////////////

DEVELOPING A VALUE MODEL OF WELLNESS SERVICE

Pei-Chen Tsai / Yi-Shin Deng / Hsiao-Chen You
Institute of Applied Arts, National Chiao-Tung University, Taiwan /
Institute of Creative Industries Design, National Cheng-Kung University, Taiwan /
Department of Multimedia Design, National Taichung Institute of Technology, Taiwan
pei.aa99g@nctu.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to develop a value model of wellness service. In this study, those persons who work in health care systems were recruited to participate in interviews for investigating the value of various roles and the effects of these values between the roles. Throughout this study, the flow model, sequence model and cultural model were established to explain the relationship between the different roles, the process being influenced by others, and the effects of other values in wellness-related activities. According to the models, the following features of value in wellness activities could be found: personal, interactive and temporal. Based on the result of this study, the investigating and presenting the relevance of effects between values more completely will be researched in the next study.

Key words: Wellness, Value Models, Service Design

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, health care systems often emphasize the diagnosis and treatment of disease. Currently, the focus of health care systems has been gradually extended from treatment only to both prevention and treatment of disease; hence, service that can include medical treatment, care and wellness are becoming increasingly important. In order to provide such an integrated wellness service, a wellness and preventive system should support people's health and wellness activities and satisfy their individual values in regard to engaging in it.

In the aspect of User-Centered Design, the core concept of an innovative wellness service should

start from social concern. With mutual care between communities, users are persuaded to attend to their life and improve their well being. In order to define what goals of wellness service should be provided to users, the values impacted by users' wellness activities have to be discussed, and users' requirements of wellness activities have to be explored. Accordingly, a health care system can then be designed to meet users' requirements and expectations.

Numerous value theories and models have been studied so far, especially in the management literature (Khalifa, 2004; Rokeach, 1973; Schwartz, 1994; Zeithaml, 1988). These studies emphasized individual customer value and the value which was affected by a single activity or product. However, in the context of wellness and service, factors which affect personal value may not be limited to a consumer product. Values of wellness activities should result from many people and services interacting mutually with each other.

The roles involving in a wellness service are varied, and the relationships between them are complicated. In a wellness service, requirements and expectations of physicians, nurses, patients, and hospitals are diverse. Furthermore, the individual values on perceiving wellness are multiple. The consumer value model lacks the interpretation of the complex value interactions between various roles. In the context of wellness and service, factors of individual value may not be caused by only a single consumer product. The value is a result of the interaction of the roles involved in wellness activities; the values of roles are interactive and involved with each other. In order to design a wellness service system to meet

the requirements of varied roles and such complex values structure, these issues need to be clarified.

In this study, the value in wellness activities, effects of values between individuals, and process of varying values were interpreted and discussed. The aims of this study were to explore the value of wellness of users, to perceive the complex value effects, and to try to develop value models of wellness. In-depth interviews were conducted to understand users' opinions of wellness, and to deeply probe users' feelings about the effect of others' wellness values. The value models in this study not only attempt to explain the value of an individual in the wellness service, but also the pattern of effects between various roles. The result of this study is providing suggestions and references for designing wellness services in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

THE SOCIAL DIMENSION OF WELLNESS

The World Health Organization (WHO) defined health in terms of wellness as "physical, mental, and social well-being, not merely the absence of disease" (WHO, 1958). The following studies in wellness are not confined to the absence of disease. Hettler (1984) created a hexagon model to describe 6 characteristics of wellness: physical, emotional, spiritual, occupational, intellectual, and social. These 6 characteristics are the components which were most mentioned in the studies of wellness theory models (Roscoe, 2009). What wellness recommends is not only health, but also a spiritual and environmental quality lifestyle.

In the definition of social wellness Hettler (1980), emphasized relationships among individuals with others and the environment. The relationships include common welfare (e.g., volunteer work and community support), interdependence with others and nature (e.g., social interaction and connection with nature). Hettler considered a socially well individual as one who lives in harmony with others with mutual respect and cooperation. Social wellness involves the promotion of a healthy environment, improvement of communities, effective communication, relationship with others' wellness,

and balance between individuals, other people, communities, and nature.

To compare the relationship among individuals, communities and environment, Adams et al.'s (1997) concept of social wellness is more focused on interaction between individuals. Adams et al.'s definition of social wellness is the amount of added value from received support and reciprocation, in other words, the actions of giving and receiving. Renger et al.'s (2000) social wellness concept also emphasizes the interaction between individuals and others; their view of social wellness was extended to how an individual relates to others' wellbeing, through their willingness to express their feelings, needs and opinions. Besides the core concept, support, fulfilling relationships and intimacy, Renger et al. offer a concept similar to Hettler's concept: That social wellness also included interactions with the social environment and making a contribution to the community.

Leafgren (1990) described the meaning of social wellness as constructed on the relationship to the environment to achieve common welfare, as well as awareness of, and actions to satisfy, others' needs. Crose et al. (1992) defined social wellness as a quality related to the extent of an individual's social network and history of significant relationships. Dulark (2000) mentioned that the capacity of social wellness included peer acceptance, altruism, attachments/bonds with others, and social skills (communication, assertiveness and conflict resolution).

From the above definition, social wellness involves the quality and extent of interaction with others and the interdependence between the individual and community as well as nature. Furthermore, the concept of social wellness contains the skills and comfort of interpersonal relationships, as well as the motivation, action, intent, and perception of those interactions. Providing support for others, receiving others' support, and respect for others are within the scope of social wellness. By comprehending the definitions of social wellness, the importance of social interaction is clearly described. In this study, the value of an individual's wellness and effects

related to people’s wellness value were the subject of interpretation herein.

CUSTOMER VALUE

The aim of this study was to probe the value of roles in wellness activities; hence the studies related to value and value models are the key literatures of this study.

Rokeach (1973) mentioned that value is derived from cultural, social, public groups, and individual personality. Schwartz (1994) summarized the five main features of the basic value concepts from the literature as follows: values are beliefs; values are a construct with motivation; values transcend specific actions and situations but remain abstract goals; values guide the selection or evaluation of actions, policies, people and events; and values are ordered by importance relative to one another.

Zeithaml (1988) defined customer value as customers’ evaluation of products’ effectiveness from the perception of reception and payment. Holbrook (1996) indicated that customer value has characteristics of interaction, relativity, preference, and experience. “Interaction” means that customer value exists in the space between a customer and a product. “Relativistic” means that customer value is comparative (among objects), personal (across people), and situational (specific to the context); “Preference” means the general concept of an evaluative judgment occurring when purchasing. “Experience” means that customer value is derived from the consumption experience instead of the purchase. Based on the literature reviews, the characters and relevance of value can be comprehended. However, the studies have focused on the values of a single role, consumers, and they still lack the interpretation of complex interactions between mutual value effects.

Khalifa (2004) grouped definitions of customer value into three categories, each with variations: value components models, utilitarian or benefits/costs ratio models, and means-end models. Means-end theory postulates that there are linkages between product attributes, consequence produced through consumption, and personal values of consumers, and

the value related to the decision-making processes (Gutman, 1991). It is an effective method to investigate customers’ consumer psychology and behavior (Gutman, 1982). Woodruff (1997) studied customer value with means-end chain and developed a hierarchical model to explain the effects progress between individuals’ value and consumer behavior. In this study, the construct of means-end chain was used to help researchers investigate individuals’ value more efficiently.

Figure 1. Woodruff’s (1997) customer value hierarchy model.

METHOD

In this study, the emphasis is on people’s valuation of wellness activities and mutual effects between people’s values. Case studies are discussed in this study. In-depth interviewing is conducted to capture various role requirements and expectations in regard to wellness and wellness activities. The motivation, background and context of people’s participation in wellness activities are comprehended. People’s perception, attitudes, opinions, and values regarding wellness are the important issues to be drawn out. Lastly, the model which represents the interactive situation of value between people in wellness systems is established.

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW

In order to capture the data on people’s opinions toward wellness, an in-depth interview was conducted in this study. Ladder interview is the most common method to construct mean-ends chains, especially in the field of marketing. This technique is used to find unconscious motives and what values inspire the consumption. It can help researchers to meaningfully connect product attributes with consumers’ values (Gutman, 1988). During the

interviews of this study, the ladder interview helped the host to lead participants to express their value in relation to wellness. Furthermore, a semi-structured interview was conducted in this study. Before conducting interviews with different people, different interview guides were prepared. The goal of different interview guides is to help the host frame an axis of questions for different roles in wellness care systems, and around the questions on the interaction with these roles.

RECRUITING THE PARTICIPANTS

In order to explore the complexity of values between people, different personnel who act in health care systems were recruited to participate in interviews in this study. There were 6 participants recruited to participate in each one-on-one interview, including 1 doctor, 1 nurse, 2 chronic disease patients, and 2 of their family. Through interviewing with different roles, the values of the various roles, the influence of the various values in relation to wellness activities can be observed and analyzed in depth.

ANALYSIS

After the interviews, 6 affinity diagrams were constructed according to the audio recording files. The affinity diagram is a tool used to organize ideas and data, especially in management and brainstorming. In this study, affinity diagrams were used to categorize the values of various roles. According to the pattern of the affinity diagrams, the processes of value influence and mind changing were shown clearly. After ordering the affinity diagrams, work models were established to represent the effects of values between various roles in wellness activities.

RESULTS & FINDINGS

In order to interpret the complex of mutual value effect in wellness care systems, work models were constructed to represent the results of this study. Work models were developed to represent the key aspects of a work and shown the individual perspective from customers' actual experience (Beyer & Holtzblatt, 1998). In this study, a flow

Figure 2. Consolidated flow model.

model, sequence models, and a cultural model were used to present the different aspects of mutual value effect.

THE FLOW MODEL

As shown in Fig. 2, the consolidated flow model presents various roles in wellness activities and the situation of their communication. The flow model represents the information or the effect between the roles. However, the motives, reasons and values behind the effects cannot be explained in the flow model. Besides, according to the case study, it is observed that the way that people try to influence others may be adjusted or changed depending on the different object; however, this information will not be presented in the flow model.

In the process of various roles' mutual effects, the value of a role would change with the passage of time, with the acquisition of different information, or being influenced by other people. Although the flow model can be used to explain the communicative phenomenon, it still has limits on explanations of the reasons behind the phenomena.

In the flow model of wellness activities, every role or object can be considered as the center of the model. The result is that the breakdowns become ambiguous in regard to interpreting the problem on the part of the giver or receiver.

THE SEQUENCE MODEL

The sequence model is mainly used to explain the sequence of an individual's actions. According to the case studies of this study, the various processes of different people's value effects are very complex. As Fig. 3 shows, in the process of decision-making receiving information may branch out. In a sequence model, there may be multiple bifurcation points. The sequence model is not shown only one-way; it may be organized into a complex net.

Figure 4. Consolidated sequence model.

Figure 3. Sequence model shows branches of decisions.

In wellness activities, an individual’s values are affected by others, objects or events. Figure 4, the consolidated sequence model, shows the sequence of a patient affected by his/her family and objects. In an individual’s sequence model, “Intent” is used to describe the intention that the sequence aims to achieve. However, intent is hard to define in a multiple sequence model. An individual in a passive role affected by others may not have an active intent; as well, intents may be indicated on different roles in a sequence model.

Although the process of action change can be understood in a sequence model, the pattern of

value behind the change is not represented here. Furthermore, the sequence model will be more intricate when the effects of more than two roles combined with different decisions are described.

THE CULTURAL MODEL

The cultural model is used to present the invisible and abstract expectations, desires, policies, and values. As shown in Fig. 5, the value of mutual influence and the extent of value effects in wellness activities were interpreted in a concrete way. In the figure, the arrows represent the directions of influence, but it is hard to show the value and response after receiving an influence. The dynamic variation of mutual value effect is not embodied in the cultural model.

Through the process of developing value models in wellness activities, the main findings are as follows:

- An individual’s action is driven by the context of value, which affects the decision of the activities.
- Values of various roles mutually affect and interact with each other.
- The effects between roles have a characteristic of

Figure 5. Consolidated cultural model.

timeliness; an individual's values vary with the effects of others or of time.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an attempt was made to explain complex mutual value effects. The interaction of multiple values in wellness activities was interpreted according to three work models: flow model, sequence model and cultural model. According to the work models, the following features of value in wellness can be represented: personal, interactive and temporal. Determining how to completely present the complex value effects with the associated features is an issue worthy of future discussion.

A further research of this study will supplement the survey of other roles' value and carry out an investigation with workbooks. A model which can be used to more completely explain the pattern of complex value effects will be developed next. The results of this study may serve as reference for future designs of health care services or other social interaction platforms.

REFERENCE

- Adams, T., Bezner, J., & Steinhardt, M. (1997). The conceptualization and measurement of perceived wellness: Integrating balance across and within dimensions. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 11, 208-218.
- Beyer, H., & Holtzblatt, K. (1998). *Contextual design: Defining customer-centered systems*. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.
- Croese, R., Nicholas, D. R., Gobble, D. C., & Frank, B. (1992). Gender and wellness: A multidimensional systems model for counseling. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 71, 149-156.
- Durlak, J. A. (2000). Health promotion as a strategy in primary prevention. In D. Cicchetti, J. Rappaport, I. Sandler, & R. P. Weissberg (Eds.), *The promotion of wellness in children and adolescents* (pp. 221-241). Washington, DC: CWLA Press.
- Gutman, J. (1982). A means-end chain model based on consumer categorization processes. *Journal of Marketing* 46, pp. 60-72
- Gutman, J. (1991). Exploring the nature of linkages between consequences and values, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 22, pp. 143-8.
- Hettler, B. (1980). Wellness promotion on a university campus: Family and community health. *Journal of Health Promotion and Maintenance*, 3, 77-95.
- Hettler, W. (1984). Wellness: Encouraging a lifetime pursuit of excellence. *Health Values: Achieving High Level Wellness*, 8, 13-17.
- Holbrook, M. B. (1996). Special Session Summary: Customer Value - A Framework for Analysis and Research. *Advances in Consumer Research* 23: 138-142.
- Khalifa, A.S. (2004). Customer value: a review of recent literature and an integrative configuration, *Management Decision*, Vol. 42 No.5, pp.645-66.
- Leafgren, F. (1990). Being a man can be hazardous to your health: Life-styles issues. In D. Moore & F. Leafgren (Eds.), *Problemsolving strategies and interventions for men in conflict* (pp. 265-311). Alexandria, VA: American Association for Counseling and Development.
- Renger, R. F., Midyett, S. J., Mas, F. G., Erin, T. E., McDermott, H. M., Papenfuss, R. L., Eichling, et al. (2000). Optimal Living Profile: An inventory to assess health and wellness. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 24, 403-412.
- Reynolds, T.J., Gutman, J. (1988) "Laddering theory, method, analysis, and interpretation", *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol.28 No.1 pp11-31
- Rokeach M. (1973). *The Nature of Human Values*, New York: Macmillan.
- Roscoe, L. J. (2009). Wellness: A review of theory and measurement for counselors. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 87, 216-226.
- Schwartz, S. H. (1994). Are there universal aspects in the structure and contents of human values? *Journal of Social Issues*, 50(4), 19-46.
- Woodruff, R. B. (1997). Customer value: the next source for competitive advantage, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 25 No. 2, pp. 139-53.
- Zeithaml, V. A. (1988). Consumer Perceptions of Price, Quality And Value: A Means-End Model And Synthesis of Evidence. *Journal of Marketing* 52 (July): 2-22.